

Software Vulnerability Fix Prioritization for x/rApps

Loukas Kopanias*, Stefanos Vlachos[†], Nicholas Kolokotronis[‡] and Costas Vassilakis[§]

Department of Informatics and Telecommunications

University of the Peloponnese

Tripoli, Greece

Email: *loukas.kopanias@uop.gr, [†]dit2202dsc@go.uop.gr, [‡]nkolok@uop.gr, [§]costas@uop.gr

Abstract—xApps and rApps are essential elements of the 6G framework, allowing for integration of AI-based functionality within the Open RAN (O-RAN) architecture, enhancing intelligence, automation and programmability. Their positioning in the O-RAN architecture enables them to access important resources of the 6G framework, therefore the security of xApps and rApps is critical. However, software programs may entail security issues, and security budget or roll-out time constraints may preclude the elimination of all identified issues, leading thus to residual impact, owing to security issues that are not fixed. In this paper, we present a method for prioritizing the fixing of security issues, in order to minimize the residual impact. The proposed method takes into account the attributes of the identified security issues, the relative importance of the confidence, integrity, and availability security dimensions, as well as the available security budget.

Index Terms—6G network security, xApps, rApps, residual impact, security issue prioritization, integer programming.

I. INTRODUCTION

xApps (Near-RT Apps) and rApps (Non-RT Apps) are essential elements of the 6G framework, aiming to facilitate the integration of AI-based functionality within the Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) architecture. xApps and rApps enable intelligent, automated and programmable network operations, promoting adaptive, energy efficient and optimal function of the 6G network. In particular, rApps are applications that run on the non-real-time RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) to enable broader network management, automation, and non-real-time optimization, while xApps are applications that run on the Near-RT RIC to perform rapid, dynamic, and localized optimization.

By virtue of their placement, x/rApps have access to important services and data of the O-RAN architecture, while the correctness and continuity of their functionality is critical for the error-free and optimal operation of the 6G network. In this context, it is imperative that software defects that undermine the confidentiality, the integrity and the availability –i.e. each of the security dimensions– of the x/rApps are identified and addressed. While, however, the identification of software defects can be facilitated by different tools, including static application security testing (SAST) tools [1], [2] and dynamic application security testing (DAST) tools [3], in many cases it is infeasible to address the entire set of identified issues, due to limitations in security budget or restrictions on the roll-out time. Therefore, developers and CIOs need to select a subset of issues that will be fixed in the target time frame, while the remaining ones will be addressed at a later stage.

The fact that some security issues will be present in the deployed x/rApp introduces a level of risk for the operation of the x/rApp, and consequently for the functionality and security of the O-RAN framework. Since it is desirable that this level of risk is minimized, the process of selecting the subset of issues that will be fixed should be tailored to serve this goal. In this paper, we present an algorithm for prioritizing the fixing of security issues, aiming to minimize the *residual risk*, i.e. the risk that is owing to the software defects that are not addressed. The proposed algorithm advances the state-of-the-art by taking into account the importance of the security dimensions (confidence, integrity, and availability) and the exploitability of each security issue, while also refining the approach for estimating the impact of the issues on security, compared to existing algorithms [4]. The proposed approach has been evaluated against open-source x/rApps and has proven to reduce the residual risk in comparison to baseline algorithms, allowing for tailoring of priorities according to the importance of the security dimensions.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: Section II overviews related work, while Section III presents the proposed algorithm. Section IV reports on our experiments aiming to substantiate and quantify the performance of the proposed approach, while Section V concludes the paper and outlines future work.

II. RELATED WORK

The rapid increase in publicly disclosed vulnerabilities has significantly complicated vulnerability management processes in modern software systems and network infrastructures. Traditional vulnerability management frameworks primarily rely on severity-based scoring mechanisms such as the Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS) [5], [6] to guide remediation priorities. While CVSS provides standardized metrics for evaluating exploitability and impact, several studies have demonstrated that severity scores alone are insufficient for accurate risk prioritization in complex operational environments [4], [7].

To address these limitations, researchers have explored risk-based vulnerability prioritization approaches that incorporate additional contextual attributes. Early studies on vulnerability lifecycle analysis revealed that only a small subset of disclosed vulnerabilities are actively exploited in real-world attacks, suggesting that remediation strategies should consider exploitation likelihood in addition to severity [8], [9]. Large-scale

empirical analyses further showed that exploit availability and vulnerability age significantly influence the probability of exploitation [10], [11].

Farris et al. [12] proposed the VULCON framework that formulates vulnerability prioritization as an optimization problem that minimizes organizational exposure to vulnerabilities. It introduces metrics such as Time-to-Vulnerability Remediation (TVR) and Total Vulnerability Exposure (TVE) to guide patch scheduling under resource constraints. Using vulnerability scan results and asset information, VULCON applies multi-objective optimization to determine remediation priorities and has demonstrated measurable reductions in overall vulnerability exposure.

Anjum et al. [13] proposed a framework based on the fuzzy Best–Worst Method (BWM) to rank vulnerabilities using weighted evaluation criteria. The approach integrates fuzzy logic to address uncertainty in expert judgments and has shown improved consistency compared with traditional methods such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) [14].

More recently, data-driven approaches have been proposed to improve vulnerability prioritization by predicting exploitation likelihood. Machine learning techniques have been used to analyze historical vulnerability data and identify patterns associated with exploited vulnerabilities [15]. For example, Bozorgi et al. applied supervised learning methods to predict exploit availability using vulnerability features [15]. Later work incorporated additional signals such as social media activity and vulnerability disclosure timelines to improve exploit prediction accuracy [16]. The LICALITY framework combines vulnerability likelihood and criticality using neural learning and probabilistic reasoning to estimate exploitation probability and potential impact. By leveraging historical exploitation data and attacker behavior patterns, it prioritizes vulnerabilities that are more likely to be exploited in real-world scenarios [17].

The work in [4] provides security fix prioritization through the application of integer optimization techniques. Initially, this algorithm estimates the impact each software issue by computing an average of impacts over relevant entries of the National Vulnerability Database (NVD, <https://nvd.nist.gov/>), and subsequently uses this estimate as a weight related to the decision to fix the specific issue in the integer optimization problem.

Several surveys have systematically analyzed vulnerability prioritization and prediction techniques. These studies categorize existing approaches into severity-based, exploitability-based, contextual, and predictive models, highlighting the need for dynamic and scalable prioritization methods capable of handling large vulnerability datasets and complex infrastructures [18], [19].

Despite these advances, most existing approaches primarily focus on estimating vulnerability severity, exploitability likelihood, or remediation efficiency. Limited attention has been given to evaluating the residual risk that remains after mitigation actions are applied, particularly in large-scale distributed systems and emerging network architectures. As

modern infrastructures become increasingly complex, effective vulnerability management requires prioritization methods that not only identify critical vulnerabilities but also minimize the residual risk that persists after mitigation efforts.

III. SECURITY FIX PRIORITIZATION

The goal of the prioritization phase is to propose a list of issues that will be fixed in a way that:

- the total effort needed to perform the fixes is less than or equal to the total security budget;
- the *residual weighted impact*, i.e. the vulnerability impact that will remain present in the system after the designated issues are fixed is minimized. The computation of the residual weighted impact takes into account the impact of the security issues that will not be fixed (due to security budget constraints) on the three security dimensions, plus the relative importance of each security dimension for the particular $x/rApp$.

The prioritization of security fixes step is conducted using integer linear programming [20]. In more detail, the system formulates an integer linear programming optimization (ILPO) problem, where the goal of the optimization is to minimize the residual weighted impact, whereas the adherence to the total security budget is modeled as a constraint. In the following paragraphs, the formulation of the ILPO problem is analyzed in detail. The aspects taken into account for the formulation of the ILPO problem are described below, whereas Table I lists the notations used in the ILPO problem.

- the impact of each the security issue on confidentiality, integrity and availability.
- the technical debt associated with each security issue, i.e. the time needed to fix it, expressed in working hours.
- the exploitability score ES_i , reflecting how easy it is for a threat agent to successfully take advantage of the software issue.
- the relative importance of each security dimension for the particular $x/rApp$; this is expressed as a triple (W_C, W_I, W_A) , where the elements represent the weights of the confidence, integrity, and availability dimensions, respectively. The weights are normalized so that $W_C + W_I + W_A = 1$.
- the total security budget available; this is expressed in working hours.

The values of I_i^C , I_i^I and I_i^A for each security issue are estimated based on the historical records of CVEs owing to the same root causes, as the latter are codified through the Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE), i.e. the classification of the coding faults that cause vulnerabilities, such as use of weak cryptography, buffer overruns or deserialization of untrusted data. In more detail, for a specific vulnerability S_i , we retrieve from the NVD the CWE ids of the coding errors that have led to the existence of S_i . Subsequently, we retrieve from the NVD all security issues v which are owing to any of these CWE ids. For each of the retrieved issues v , we calculate a similarity score with S_i via the Jaccard similarity metric [21],

TABLE I
NOTATIONS USED FOR ILPO PROBLEM FORMULATION

Notation	Description
S_i	The i^{th} security issue
N	The number of security issues detected
SB	The available security budget, expressed in available working hours
I_i^C	The impact of S_i on confidentiality
I_i^I	The impact of S_i on integrity
I_i^A	The impact of S_i on availability
EW_i	The exploitability weight element of the i^{th} security issue.
FT_i	The time needed to fix S_i , expressed in working hours
W_C	The relative importance of the confidence dimension
W_I	The relative importance of the integrity dimension
W_A	The relative importance of the availability dimension
x_i	An output variable of the problem; x_i is set to 1 if security budget is allocated to fixing S_i , otherwise x_i is set to 0.

which compares the resemblance between the sets of CWEs that pertain to each of the vulnerabilities. More specifically,

$$sim(v, S_i) = \frac{|CWE(v) \cap CWE(S_i)|}{|CWE(v) \cup CWE(S_i)|} \quad (1)$$

where $CWE(x)$ is the set of weaknesses to which vulnerability x is owing. According to this formulation, two vulnerabilities are considered more similar if they are owing to the exact same weaknesses, while the existence of disjoint weaknesses lowers the similarity score. Then, the impact of S_i on security dimension SD is computed as the weighted average of the impact that each of the matching vulnerabilities v on SD . Formally, the impact of security issue S_i on security dimension $SD \in \{C, I, A\}$ is computed as:

$$I_i^{SD} = \frac{\sum_{v \in V_i} I_v^{SD} * sim(v, S_i)}{\sum_{v \in V_i} *sim(v, S_i)} \quad (2)$$

where V_i is the set of vulnerabilities in the NVD [22] that have at least one common weakness (CWE) with S_i , and $sim(v, S_i)$ is an evaluation of similarity between a vulnerability $v \in NVD$ and S_i .

For a vulnerabilities $v \in NVD$, its impact I_v^{SD} on a particular security dimension SD is computed from v 's CVSS 3.1 record, considering impact designation (HIGH, LOW, NONE) for the particular dimension, and taking into account the scope change, temporal and environmental metrics, following the methodology applied for the CVSS score computation [23].

Please note that different versions of CVSS result in different scorings for the same vulnerability ([24] reports that CVSS v4.0 has an average score that is about 10% higher than CVSS v3.1), it is important that all vulnerability impact scores are computed according to the same version of the CVSS standard. We also note that other databases can be used instead of NVD, e.g. the Open Source Vulnerabilities database (OSV, <https://osv.dev/>), provided that the selected database provides information on the impact of vulnerabilities and their root causes (CWEs).

A. ILPO problem formulation

As noted above, the prioritization phase will select a (sub)set of the existing security issues to be fixed, and the cost of fixing the i^{th} security issue S_i is FT_i . Therefore, if S_i is selected to be fixed (which is determined by the value of output variable x_i), a cost of FT_i will be incurred, whereas if S_i will remain unfixed, no cost will be sustained. Therefore the total cost TC of fixing the selected issues is:

$$TC = \sum_{i=1}^N FT_i * x_i \quad (3)$$

Since the upper bound of the total cost is the available security budget SB , the constraint

$$\sum_{i=1}^N FT_i * x_i \leq SB \quad (4)$$

is added to the ILPO problem. Concerning the calculation of the residual weighted impact RWI , this will be owing to the security issues that will remain unfixed, i.e. the issues for which x_i will be zero. Since the importance of each security dimension is potentially different, the weights W_C, W_I and W_A are used to capture this aspect, therefore the residual weighted impact for S_i is:

$$RWI_i = (I_C(i) * W_C + I_I(i) * W_I + I_A(i) * W_A) * (1 - x_i) \quad (5)$$

In order to accommodate the exploitability aspect of the security issue, we utilize *exploitability score* ES field of the NVD CVSS 3.1 records. This field is an assessment of the potential of a threat agent to successfully take advantage of the vulnerability. The exploitability weight EW_i of issue S_i is computed analogously to the computation of the impact of security dimensions (c.f. Equation 2) i.e.:

$$EW_i = \frac{1}{4} * \frac{\sum_{v \in V_i} ES_v * sim(v, S_i)}{\sum_{v \in V_i} *sim(v, S_i)} \quad (6)$$

The weighted sum in Equation 6 is multiplied by the constant 1/4 to normalize it in the range [0, 1], since the range of the exploitability score in the NVD records is [0,4].

Combining the last two equations we obtain the final residual weighted impact for S_i which is expressed as:

$$RWI_i = (I_C(i) * W_C + I_I(i) * W_I + I_A(i) * W_A) * (1 - x_i) * EW_i \quad (7)$$

Since the goal of the prioritization phase is to minimize the overall weighted impact, the following optimization goal is added to the ILPO problem:

$$minimize \sum_{i=1}^N RWI_i \quad (8)$$

In this work, we focus on vulnerabilities that can be exploited remotely; therefore, issues whose attack vectors are “network” or “adjacent” will be included in the prioritization process, whereas issues whose attack vectors are “local” or “physical” will be excluded. It is noted that issues with attack vectors

equal to “physical” are exploitable by insiders, or by threat agents that have physical access to the installation. Please note that while the 6G network involves edge devices, x/rApps run on the RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC), hence any exploitation of edge devices does not render an x/rApp vulnerability with a “physical” attack vector directly exploitable. The investigation of the possible interplay between compromises of edge devices and the exploitation of x/rApp vulnerabilities is considered part of our future work.

Similarly, issues whose attack vector is “local” are exploitable by legitimate users of the affected software (who are entitled to access), or by remote threat agents who have successfully exploited some vulnerability with “network” or “adjacent” attack vector to gain an initial access to the system. Attack graphs [25] may be exploited to ensure a more comprehensive modeling of exploitable vulnerabilities in the software; this aspect will be addressed in our future work.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

In order to validate the applicability of the proposed algorithm and quantify the gains offered by its application, an experiment was conducted to assess: (a) whether the application of the algorithm reduces the weighted residual risk of x/rApps and (b) whether the algorithm surpasses the performance of baseline algorithms.

In the experiment performed, a number of open-source x/rApps sourced from Github.com were used. Each x/rApp was analyzed using the SonarQube SAST analyzer¹, and subsequently the list of issues identified by SonarQube was retrieved. The list was then filtered to retain only security-related software issues, i.e., issues that are either flagged directly as security bugs, or affecting the reliability of the application, under the rationale that reliability is an integral part of security [26]. x/rApps found to have less than 5 issues were excluded from further processing, since a very low number of issues severely limits the potential of optimization algorithms to formulate beneficial prioritizations. Then, for x/rApps retained, the prioritization algorithm was applied, and statistics regarding (a) the weighted residual risk reduction and (b) the use of the security budget were collected. Table II lists the x/rApps used in the experiment, listing also, for each of the applications, the number of security-related issues identified by SonarQube, and the technical debt associated with the fixing of these issues.

Before running the prioritization algorithm, an analysis was performed to gain insight into the correlation between the magnitudes of impact of software issues on different security dimensions. The results of the analysis are illustrated in Table III. This table asserts that the impact on each individual dimension is positively correlated with the total impact of the issue, which is expected since higher impacts per dimension lead to higher total impacts. However, there are two inter-dimension correlations, namely confidentiality vs. availability and integrity vs. availability, which are negative. This finding

substantiates the need to take into account impacts on individual security dimensions when prioritizing fixes. Indeed, when only the total impact of software issues is considered, opting to fix an issue S_y with a very high impact on confidentiality and availability and no impact on integrity, over an issue S_z with medium impact on integrity and no impact on the other dimensions is a beneficial decision. However, if the integrity dimension of the software is considered of high importance and the other two dimensions are deemed much less significant, this choice will not be beneficial, S_z should be prioritized over S_y . The analysis results confirm that such cases will occur with a high probability.

Issue prioritization for each x/rApp was performed under different conditions, to simulate (a) varying weights of the three security dimensions and (b) diverse security budget availabilities. In particular:

- For parameters W_c , W_i , W_a grid search [27] was applied, with each parameter taking values from the set $\{0, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1\}$, subject to the constraint $W_c + W_i + W_a = 1$.
- the available security budget was set to the values $\{25\%, 50\% \text{ and } 75\%\}$ of the total budget needed to fix all security issues in the software.

Besides assessing the prioritization of each x/rApp in isolation, an additional setup was created, which contained all issues identified in the individual x/rApps. This setup corresponds to a combined deployment, where the goal is to minimize the weighted residual risk for the system as a whole.

The performance of the proposed algorithm is compared against the following baselines:

- the prioritization algorithm used in [4], where the impact on individual security dimensions and exploitability are not considered. This algorithm will be denoted as $Pri_{uniform}$.
- a prioritization algorithm according to which issues are prioritized considering the “severity” designation provided by SonarQube. In particular, issues tagged as having “BLOCKING” severity are assigned top priority, followed by issues tagged as “CRITICAL”, “MAJOR”, “MINOR” and “INFO”, in that order. Notably, if all issues in a category are examined and some security budget still remains (either because all issues are allocated a security budget or because some issue(s) need more budget than the available), then this budget is used for allocation to issues in lower categories. This algorithm will be denoted as $Pri_{severity}$.
- a prioritization algorithm allocating budget to the issues in the order in which they are reported by SonarQube. This algorithm will be denoted as $Pri_{sequential}$.

Figure 1 depicts the performance of the four algorithms for each tested x/rApp setup. The weighted residual risk reduction illustrated for each configuration in this graph is an average of all security dimension weights and budget specifications used for the particular configuration. In this graph we can observe that the proposed algorithm consistently outperforms

¹<https://sonarcloud.io/>

TABLE II
X/RAPPS USED IN THE EXPERIMENT

x/rApp	Type	Description	# issues	Total debt
flexirc	Foundation	Underpinning for x/rApps [†]	57	690
kpm_rc-xapp	xApp	xApp with KPM v2.03 [‡]	11	130
nonrttric-rapp-ransliceassurance	rApp	O-RAN-SC Non-RealTime RIC [§]	9	280
ric-app-kpimon-go	xApp	RIC KPI monitoring application [#]	10	190

[†] <https://github.com/openaicellular/flexirc>

[‡] https://github.com/mirazabal/kpm_rc-xapp

[§] <https://github.com/o-ran-sc/nonrttric-rapp-ransliceassurance>

[#] <https://github.com/o-ran-sc/ric-app-kpimon-go>

TABLE III
CORRELATION BETWEEN SOFTWARE ISSUE IMPACT ON DIFFERENT SECURITY DIMENSIONS

Dimensions	Correlation / p-value
Total impact vs Confidentiality impact	0.415 / $1.7 * 10^{-5}$
Total impact vs Integrity impact	0.5813 / $2.27 * 10^{-10}$
Total impact vs Availability impact	0.4775 / $5.08 * 10^{-7}$
Confidentiality impact vs. Integrity impact	0.96 / $1.2 * 10^{-13}$
Confidentiality impact vs. Availability impact	-0.5686 / $6.75 * 10^{-10}$
Integrity impact vs. Availability impact	-0.4012 / $3.5 * 10^{-5}$

all other baselines. Compared to the $Pri_{uniform}$ algorithm [4], the proposed algorithm demonstrates the capability to adapt to the different weight specifications, leading to relative performance gains from 5.51% (*flexirc* xApp) to 8.63% (*ric-app-kpimon-go* xApp). The corresponding performance edge of the proposed algorithm against the $Pri_{severity}$ algorithm ranges from 8.63% (*ric-app-kpimon-go* xApp) to 49.68% (combined setup). Finally, the proposed algorithm outperforms the $Pri_{sequential}$ algorithm by a margin ranging from 6.10% (*nonrttric-rapp-ransliceassurance* rApp) to 138.60% (*flexirc* xApp). It is worth noting that the proposed algorithm achieves this reduction while using a slightly lower proportion of the available security budget (92.8% on average, against 92.9% for the $Pri_{uniform}$ algorithm, 93.1% for the $Pri_{severity}$ algorithm and 93.3% for the $Pri_{sequential}$ algorithm). This demonstrates that the proposed algorithm can direct the use of the available budget more effectively. It is worth noting that the prioritization recommended by the proposed algorithm reduces the weighted residual risk in all cases, achieving the maximum reduction among all baselines, hence the proposed approach demonstrates increased effectiveness regarding residual risk reduction.

Figure 1 illustrates the performance of the four algorithms for each security budget level, to provide insight on the gains offered by the proposed algorithm depending on the available resources. We can observe that generally, for smaller budgets the performance edge of the proposed algorithm is larger. This is owing to the fact that under strict budget restrictions, the efficient utilization of the resources is more important, compared to cases where resources are in abundance. At

Fig. 1. Weighted residual risk reduction by x/rApp

a security budget level of 25%, the performance edge of the proposed algorithm ranges from 3.7% ($Pri_{uniform}$) to 89.5% ($Pri_{sequential}$); the performance edge is narrowed when the budget level increases to 50%, varying from 4.1% to ($Pri_{uniform}$) to 44.4% ($Pri_{sequential}$), while it is further confined to a window between 3.5% ($Pri_{uniform}$) and 22.3% ($Pri_{sequential}$) at a security budget level of 75%.

To assess whether the observed differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant, we conducted pairwise comparisons using the Anova test, considering all cases of weight assignments to dimensions. Table IV reports the resulting p-values for the comparison between the proposed algorithms and each of the baselines. We can observe that for all comparisons statistical significance can be established, either at 0.01 or at the 0.05 level.

It should be noted that the proposed algorithm exhibits the best performance in all individual cases examined in the context of the experiment. In a number of cases, it is tied

Fig. 2. Weighted residual risk reduction by security budget

TABLE IV
STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PERFORMANCE C

Compared algorithms	p-value	Comment
<i>Proposed vs. Pri_uniform</i>	0.03	Statistically significant at p=0.05
<i>Proposed vs. Pri_severity</i>	1.9×10^{-4}	Statistically significant at p=0.01
<i>Proposed vs. Pri_sequential</i>	5.2×10^{-14}	Statistically significant at p=0.01

in the first place with the $Pri_{uniform}$ algorithm, while more rarely a triple tie occurs.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented an algorithm for the prioritization of fixes for software security issues. The proposed algorithm estimates the impact of each security issue on the individual security dimensions as well as its exploitability, and subsequently uses these estimations, in conjunction with the technical debt associated with each issue, the available security budget, the relative importance of each individual security dimension to recommend a set of fixes that, under a specified budget, minimize the residual weighted impact. The effectiveness of the proposed algorithm has been evaluated in the context of 6G O-RAN x/rApps, and has proven to be more effective than baseline algorithms, achieving higher reductions of the residual weighted impact, while also managing to slightly reduce the amount of resources needed.

A limitation of the present work is the reliance on the SonarQube SAST tools. The work in [28] reports that SAST tools exhibit recall values between 0.34 and 0.57, therefore, a number of security issues may be missed. In our future work we will consider the combined use of multiple SAST tools, in order to maximize the recall of software security issues.

Future work will also focus on improving the estimation of the impact of each security issue on the individual security dimensions, exploiting additional features of the software issue (e.g. number of lines, language, complexity etc.), as well

as the exploitation of automated vulnerability security fixes using automated sanitization or simple code replacements [29], or employing more elaborate methods e.g. LLMs [30]. The incorporation of attack graphs [25] to more accurately estimate the probability that a specific vulnerability is exploited will be also examined. Since the logic of the algorithm is not specific to xApps/rApps, the effectiveness of the algorithm for software applications in different contexts will be also evaluated experimentally. Finally, the security landscape of O-RAN applications will be surveyed, in order to gain insight on the types of issues typically present in x/rApps and formulate strategies for developer training and awareness.

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